

Intelligent Adaptative Robotic System for Physical Interaction Tasks

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Abstract—Big steps in the last years have been made in robotics. From mobile robots for home tasks to fully automatized systems in industrial environments.

In the beginning, the main focus of robotics was to provide robotics solutions to tackle the necessity of improving both, productivity in repetitive tasks and safeguarding people in dangerous environments. Nowadays, following the advances in technology and industry 4.0, these objectives have changed to more demanding ones. These require flexible and autonomous intelligent solutions, i.e. systems capable of performing a variety of tasks with the minimum programming or system specifications. With the rise of Artificial Intelligence, novel algorithms have been developed, and let improve robotics systems capabilities by becoming more intelligent and autonomous.

The aim of this work is the development of an adaptative intelligent robotic system for physical interaction tasks. In this kind of task, the robot has a strong physical interaction with the environment, driving dynamical requirements to fulfill the task. To achieve this, a Three system framework made up of control, monitoring, and adaptative systems is proposed.

Index Terms—Robotics, physical interaction task, compliant controller, reinforcement learning, monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic systems are widely used in the industry, helping to automate and improve productivity in many sectors. Notwithstanding current trends in consumer and social demands, are related to customized products with low volumes of production. These requirements drive the necessity of flexible and adaptable systems.

Robotic systems need a description of both, the environment and the robot kinematics and dynamics. The kinematics and dynamic description of the robot is well defined and have a strong theoretical background in the literature. On the other hand, the environment and task description are widely studied, but the easiness or difficulty of the model depends directly on the specific environment and task properties and requirements.

In compliant control architectures, many parameters are needed to be set, in order to determine the dynamic behavior between the robot end-effector and the environment. These parameters are set manually by the user, according to the task and its requirements. For a specific task and

environment characteristics, these controllers present a good performance. Notwithstanding working in non-structured or unknown environments, the tasks and environment characteristics are continuously changing, and due to that, force and position specifications are changing. For that reason, an adjustment in the controller parameters is needed. e.g. in a disassembly process of the recycling chain, where many types of products with different conditions arrive in the process, requires customized force or trajectories specifications.

Usually, fixed parameters are determined according to specific task requirements. If the environment changes, these parameters will cause inadequate results or poor performance. A new set of parameters are required to adapt the systems to the new task requirements. To achieve flexible and autonomous systems, the necessity of self-adaptation to face the tasks changes is needed.

Using compliant controllers, the robot is able to be compliant with the environment. Despite that, these control methodologies are restricted to the task characteristics that was used for the parameter setting. But for different task characteristics such as weight, geometries, etc. these parameters are no longer adequate for an appropriate performance of the system.

To achieve the control adaptation, classic adaptative methodologies use parametric methods to achieve the parameter tuning, i.e. letting the parameter selection dependent on a variable, e.g. the weight in the pick and place applications. With these, all the control parameters selection will be dependent on these variables [1]. These classical variable approaches present good performance in many applications but requires a model of the variable approach or a model of the task, and these require hard work and engineering expertise to achieve good results.

With the rise in the field of artificial intelligence in the last years, novel proposals have been made for self-tuning of the parameter and self-learning of the environment characteristics. Specially showing good results in unstructured environments and scenarios where the algorithm was not trained [2], [3].

These kind of algorithm needs experience to improve its behavior. This achieve through trial and error, running the system and perform the task. In some cases in robotic systems this can not be done, sometimes for a time, economic or practical aspect. Simulations environments are used to face this, but is not always possible. The use of deep learning

Fig. 1. Three-stage control scheme proposal for robotic physical interaction tasks.

(DL) algorithms want to tackle this problem. In robotics DL algorithms are used to approximate value functions, which are used to RL policy improvement [4]. In that way the system can take actions from unknown situations according to similar ones.

A. Case of Study

The disassembly process in the recycling chain shows challenges where an autonomous and flexible system assuring the component integrity is needed. Different components in different states arrive to the process. Moreover, prior knowledge about the physical properties can not be known.

This work wants to tackle flexible component extraction for reuse. In this case, different states of the flexible that arrives to the plant needs, different force specifications and in many cases the position and trajectories of extractions would be different.

II. INTELLIGENT ROBOTIC SYSTEM FOR PHYSICAL INTERACTION TASKS

An intelligent adaptive system for physical interaction tasks following a three-stage framework is presented in figure 1.

First a based controller, made up by an *hybrid control* architecture is used. The positions control law used, corresponds to the own robot's inner position control. On the other hand, the force control law consists of a proportional force control loop. In that way, the final position references are made up of a combination of three references. An initial reference trajectory X_d that comes from a reference planner, the second corresponds to positions deviation actions X_a , from the reinforcement learning algorithm, and the last one is

the contribution of the force control law X_f , that guarantees the compliance between the end-effector and the environment according to the force measurements of the robot joints.

In a second stage, the *monitoring system* provides status indicators to know the actual state of the task. For the case of study proposed, elements with different physical properties have to be manipulated by the robot. To ensure the integrity of the elements that the end-effector is interacting with, meaningful status indicators are stiffness and possible directions of extraction. To the obtention of these status indicators, fusionated data from position, velocities, and force of the robot's joints is used.

The third stage correspond to an *adaptability system*, it consist in a reinforcement learning algorithm. The state space of the system is made up of the status indicators and the current position and velocities of the robot's joints. The RL action space corresponds to the adaptation of the force control law parameters K_f and F_d , and also, direct trajectory deviation X_a , to ensure a precise compliant behavior.

This system architecture will allow the system to extract flexible elements of different characteristics. The hybrid controller provides a compliant behavior of the end effector in the task. With the monitoring system, the knowledge of the actual state of the task and its characteristics will be made. Finally, the adaptive system will modify the robot's movements and control behavior to achieve a flexible and autonomous system.

III. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A three-stage framework of an intelligent adaptive system for robotic physical interaction tasks was presented. A hybrid controller guarantees the end-effector compliance with the environment. The monitoring and adaptive systems let the system adapt to the actual state of the task. In that way, a flexible and autonomous system is achieved.

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